

Association

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QTL

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Additional File 12 (.pdf)

Figure S11: Effect of minor allelic frequency distribution, SNP distributions along the genome and SNP densities on the number of associated SNP and QTL detected. Boxplots were drawn on 100 sets of 50 000 to 250 000 markers sampled according to different MAF distributions (A, B) and different SNP distributions along the genome (C, D). A, C: number of SNP associated; B, D: Number of QTL detected. In A and B, 600K_MAF (yellow), GBS_MAF (green), Low_MAF (cyan), Flat_MAF (blue), High_MAF (pink) on x axis indicate boxplots corresponding to MAF distribution similar to 600K, similar to GBS, skewed towards low MAF, flat MAF and skewed toward high MAF, respectively. In C and D, Dens_50K (red), Dens_600K (yellow), Dens_GBS (cyan), Dens_Gen (blue), Dens_Phys (pink) on x axis indicate distribution of SNPs along the genome corresponding to 50K, GBS, 600K, even genetic and physical distances, respectively. For A, B, C and D, modalities indicated as “Random” in x axis correspond to random sample of SNP. Number of markers for each boxplot are indicated after the point.